

Supplementary material: Comments on Guidance on EU Deforestation Regulation released by [European Commission \(europa.eu\)](https://european-commission.europa.eu) 2 October 2024

In response to various questions and comments the European Commission prepared a guidance document that was circulated in confidential circles in April 2024 and finally, with minor modifications, released on October 2 2024. The guidance document has a low legal status, as clarified in a footnote : “1 Nothing in this guidance document either replaces or substitutes direct reference to the instruments described and the Commission does not accept any liability for any loss or damage caused by errors or statements made in it. Only the European Court of Justice can make final judgments on the Regulation’s interpretation.”

Seven pages of the text aim to clarify key concepts of ‘deforestation’ as the start of agricultural use’

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The text was clearly written from a European perspective and frame of reference, where

- A conceptual segregation of agriculture and forest as separate sectors and actors is taken as a given and agroforestry is an afterthought, rather than part of the initial problem analysis and framing despite its role in the production of the targeted commodities outside of Europe,
- Swidden/fallow cycles are no longer part of the collective memory,
- Privatization of formerly communal land is assumed and no institutions between individuals and state are acknowledged,
- A ‘single actor, single purpose’ view on land use prevails with little understanding of multifunctional, multi-stakeholder landscapes,
- A strong belief that strongly disaggregated spatial data can be correctly interpreted in a black-white forest-agriculture language by external EUDR agents without knowledge of local context.

The text falls short of appreciating the reality of the landscapes in which large parts of the seven ‘deforestation-risk’ commodities are produced – and the differences between soybean, cattle, palm oil, cocoa, coffee and rubber production in this respect, while wood products are considered to be deforestation-free by definition and subject to forest degradation rules yet to be clarified.

There is no single reference to or appreciation for the definitional confusion that arises where ‘EUDR forest’ concepts differ from the ‘UNFCCC forest’ concepts as quantified for climate policy’, allowing for a certain degree of subsidiarity and adjustment to national circumstances in the name of policy coherence.

Yet, in a few places an underlying interest in protecting a ‘core forest’ concept as ultimate rational of the policy shines through – which could be a good direction to explore further.

In the subsequent text verbatim citations of the text are on the left side (sometimes with our highlighting and **bolding**) and our comments in boxes on the right.

3. Definition of 'Forest' Relevant legislation:

According to Article 2 (4) of the EUDR an area is considered 'forest' if the following characteristics apply:

- Land spanning more than 0.5 hectares – This means that the area of trees described by the perimeter of canopy cover reaches 0.5 hectare or beyond.
- Trees higher than 5 metres – this means that the top of the trees reaches the average height of 5 metres or more.
- Canopy cover of more than 10% - This means that the ratio of the canopy cover of the trees forming the tree stand to the area occupied by the tree stand is more than 10%.
- Trees **able to reach those thresholds in situ** – This means areas with young trees that have not yet reached but expected to reach canopy cover 10% and tree height of 5 metres. **It includes in particular areas that are temporarily unstocked due to clear-cutting as part of a forest management practice or natural disasters, and which are expected to be regenerated.**
- **Excluding land that is predominantly under agricultural or urban land use** – This means that the forest is determined both by the presence of trees and the absence of other predominant land use (see below and also Section 4). The land spanning, the average height, and the canopy cover characteristics must be present or able to reach these thresholds in-situ simultaneously.

Among European countries there is variation in national forest definitions, used in UNFCCC context, in all these parameters (Lawson, 2024): Area: 0.05 - 1 ha, Tree crown cover: 10-30%, tree height: 2-5 m, minimum width: unspecified-10-30 m

The 'lack of policy coherence' within each country dealing with multiple forest concepts for related policy arena's must be weighed against the relevance of uniform forest interpretations across multiple countries from which commodities can be sourced.

Where the global climate change and biodiversity agenda's are explicitly mentioned as rationale for then EUDR, subsidiarity of forest concepts both within and outside the EU would be advisable.

Provided that the characteristics in the definition are met, the area of 'forest' includes but is not limited to: **[NB bullets re-ordered for comments]**

- areas outside the legally designated forest land which meet the criteria of the definition of 'forest'.
- areas surrounded by forests or strictly connected to it used for forestry, such as forest roads, fire breaks, and other small open areas, unless they are established on their own individual real-estate property,
- nurseries of forest species grown within forest area to fulfil the forest owners' own needs;
- land abandoned generally for more than 10 years with a regeneration of trees that have reached the criteria of 'forest' (please see in

Trees outside 'forest lands' are included, while 'forest lands without trees' remain forest

The specified tree cover is not needed as long as a surrounding area is 'forest' – shifting the scale of evaluation

10 years of fallow growth makes land a 'forest' regardless of prior (and subsequent) agricultural use

connection with 'set-aside land and land under temporary fallow' (ixn Section 4);

- mangroves in tidal zones, regardless of whether this area is classified as land area or not;

Makes sense, relevant for wood products

4. Definition of 'Agricultural use' and exceptions

According to Article 2 (5) of the EUDR an area is considered under 'agricultural use' if the purpose of the land use is agriculture.

The concept of a single 'purpose' and 'land user' who can be interrogated on the purpose is problematic for 'multifunctional land use'

- Set-aside land, or land under temporary fallow which means agricultural land at prolonged rest before re-cultivation, pastoral use or use for other agricultural activities. This may be part of the agricultural holdings' crop rotation system or because legitimate reasons or exceptional circumstances such as flood damage, lack of water, unavailability of inputs, including economic, social (illness, succession problems) or legal reasons (litigation, etc). NB: Land set-aside or remaining fallow should be considered as remaining under 'agricultural use' generally for [ten] years. However, the area can be considered as remaining under 'agricultural use' for longer than this period if it is demonstrated that the agricultural activities could not be resumed because of one of the above-mentioned reasons. The reason given must cover the whole period in which the land was set-aside or under temporary fallow. If such demonstration is made, the land should be continuously considered to be under agricultural use, unless it is officially designated as forest by national law.

The description here shows limited understanding of swidden/fallow rotations as they still exist in many (sub)tropical countries, where a community institution often acts as 'owner' relative to the state, with temporary use rights for community members.

The primary reason for 'fallow' maybe recovery of soil fertility and weed control, beyond the reasons mentioned here.

The transition from swidden to fallow tends to be gradual, and harvesting (agricultural use) may continue while natural regeneration of an often woody-vegetation has started. The [ten] years could be counted from the last recorded harvest or the first year tree cover meets the stated thresholds.

Many 'secondary forests' in Sumatra, Borneo include rubber trees that have been/can be tapped when market conditions are favourable. This clause will make many of those as 'in agricultural use', and if such vegetation is replaced by intensified tree crop production post 2020, EUDR compliant. The problem is that there are no reliable spatial data to cover this clause.

- Where it can be demonstrated by adequately conclusive evidence that both (i) a plot of land was under ‘agricultural use’ as described above before 31 December 2020, and (ii) where a producer decided to plant short rotation coppice or commit the land to temporary afforestation before that date or after that date and that land does not fall under the scope of a forest management plan or legislation requiring forest management or protection of forest on that plot of land, such plot of land is deemed to remain in agricultural use for the purposes of the EUDR and the producer may continue agricultural activity on that plot of land.
- The above-mentioned agricultural land use categories can cover also surfaces occupied by landscape elements, which are encouraged for biodiversity or environmental reasons.

The burden of proof and standards of ‘adequately conclusive evidence’ here will be contested. Suggested types of evidence that can be acceptable may include:

- Age of trees (inferred from allometry or dendrochronology),
- Below-threshold tree cover before 2021,
- Pictures traceable to location
- Administrative documents traceable to location,

It would help if the EU also clarifies ‘agroforestry’ as a source of tree cover that is included in ‘agricultural use’.

This suggests recognition that trees in agroforestry landscape mosaics can be ‘multifunctional’, with agricultural production as well as conservation functionality – outside of EUDR forest concepts

Restoration, management of invasive species, forest fire prevention, animal welfare, renewable energy deployment

Land which has undergone conversion for one or several of the primary purposes listed below should **not** be understood as converted to agricultural use if the conversion has been undertaken to:

- prevent, minimise, mitigate or reverse the adverse impact on biodiversity of the introduction and spread of invasive alien species, if limited to what is strictly necessary and supported by prevention plans, management plans, or official mandates, or
- prevent, or minimise and mitigate the risk of forest fires, if limited to what is strictly necessary and supported by fire prevention plans, forest management plans, or official mandates, or
- ensure compliance with animal welfare laws where the erection of structures (permanent and non-permanent) to house animals is necessary for the purpose of ensuring their welfare and limited to the minimum necessary area for the construction, and where this activity does not impact on the categorisation of the surrounding areas as forest, or

‘Land’ here is to be read as ‘Forest’?

Fire breaks are a normal part of tree crop plantation design – will these cleared areas remain ‘forest’??

This refers to ‘sylvopastoral systems’ that are considered ‘forests’?

- ensure the restoration and subsequent conservation management of ecosystems of high biodiversity value (such as for example certain types of heathlands, wetland or grassland) if required by a conservation or restoration plan (for example a management plan of a protected area or a national or regional nature restoration plan) implementing obligations stemming from global multilateral agreements on nature and biodiversity protection and restoration such as the Convention on Biological Diversity and the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, or

- deploy renewable energy (e.g. through establishment of wind farms, photovoltaics),

even if ancillary agricultural activities may take place where essential to support the primary purpose of conversion and the land use after the conversion.

There may be a grey zone here where “agricultural land use categories can cover also surfaces occupied by landscape elements, which are encouraged for biodiversity or environmental reasons”. In several of the habitats mentioned historical agricultural use led to current conservation values – including recognized ‘heritage landscapes’

So clearing forests for solar panels is not deforestation?? How many panels are needed to invoke this clause?

The concept of ‘primary’ and ‘ancillary’ purposes appears to refer to a single user/evaluator perspective, while reality can be more complex and involve multiple actors with different priorities.

b) Clarification of the predominant land use

According to Article 2(4), in case the predominant land use is agriculture then the land does not fall under the ‘forest’ definition.

In the context of EUDR, for the purposes of the exclusions referred to in the definition of ‘forest’ in Article 2(4), ‘**agricultural use**’ should be considered predominant in the following non-exhaustive list of cases:

- Seasonal (e.g. summer grazing) or temporary silvopastoral grazing in tree covered areas which **do not fall into the category of primary forests** (e.g. in semi-natural pastures or in natural pastures with changing tree cover).
- If due to climatic conditions (e.g. temporary snow cover) silvopastoral or agrisilvicultural practices are limited to a certain period of the year, they can be considered the predominant use.
- Establishing protective groups of trees for various environmental or biodiversity purposes on a predominantly agricultural use (e.g. grazing) area, even if the area reaches the thresholds of the ‘forest’ definition.

This may well be the first place where the concept of ‘primary forest’ is introduced; it requires definition and discussion.

Evidence for this clause involves knowing the ‘purpose’ of a (past) land user, and cannot be inferred from what is directly observable.

These cases are different from ancillary agricultural activities in the context of conversion for the purpose of restoration or management of invasive alien species, which do not fall under “agricultural use”, see above.

In contrast, for the purposes of EUDR, ‘**agricultural use**’ should **not** be considered **predominant** for example in case of small-scale production of side products (e.g. coffee), and occasional extensive or occasionally small-scale grazing in forests as long as the production and related activities do not have detrimental effect on the habitat of the forest.

This clause brings in a new judgement “as long as the production and related activities do not have detrimental effect on the habitat of the forest.” On which opinions are likely to diverge

c) Definition of ‘Agricultural plantation’

‘Agricultural plantations’ are included in the definition of ‘agricultural use’ set out in Article 2(5) EUDR.

The definition of Article 2(6) of the EUDR “agricultural plantation’ refers firstly to ‘land with tree stands in agricultural production systems, such as fruit tree plantations, oil palm plantations, olive orchards” which makes reference to cropland including permanent crops as described in Section 4.

This clause refers to a FAO tradition of calling some trees ‘agricultural’ and others ‘forestry’, without clear difference in environmental functions and services. Some ‘fruit trees’ are ‘forest’ others ‘agriculture’ with a domestication continuum between them

Secondly, that definition refers to “agroforestry systems where crops are grown under tree cover”, which is explained in Section 4.d and must be read together with the exception where predominant land use does not change. Article 2 (6) EUDR further clarifies that all plantations **of relevant commodities other than wood** are encompassed under the terms ‘agricultural plantation’, therefore these plantations fall under the definition of ‘agricultural use’.

Text here suggests that ‘wood’ production implies ‘forest’, but agroforestry can be an important source of ‘wood’ as well.

Finally, Article 2 (6) EUDR lays down that agricultural plantations are excluded from the definition of ‘forest’. This means that the areas fulfilling the criteria of agricultural plantation do not fall under the definition of forest, even where they include trees such as rubber or oil palm.

For the 2025 FAO Forest Resource Assessment (FRA all rubber will be counted as ‘forest’

d) Clarification of ‘Agroforestry system’

According to FAO documents¹ ‘agroforestry’ is a collective name for land use systems and technologies where woody perennials (trees, shrubs, palms, bamboos, etc) are deliberately

¹ FAO 2003. Multilingual Thesaurus on Land Tenure. Chapter 7. Land in an agricultural, pastoral and forestry context.

used on the same land management unit as agricultural crops and/or animals, in some form of spatial arrangement or temporal sequence. In agroforestry systems there are both ecological and economic interactions between the different components. There are two basic agroforestry systems: simultaneous and sequential.

Text above suggested that swidden/fallow systems cross the 'forest' threshold after ten years of fallow – this is less than what is common practice in parts of the world

Simultaneous systems have trees and crops or animals growing together on the same piece of land, while in sequential systems crops and trees take turns in occupying most of the same space, minimising their competition.

Agroforestry can also refer to specific **forestry** practices that complement agricultural activities, such as by improving soil fertility, reducing soil erosion, improving watershed management, or providing shade and food for livestock.

This clause appears to use 'forest' where 'tree' is meant

Recital (37)² recalls that FAO definitions do not consider agroforestry systems as forests, but agricultural use and that they encompass various situations such as those where crops are grown under tree cover, as well as agrisilvicultural, silvopastoral and agrosilvopastoral systems.

Since the definition of 'forest' in Article 2(4) of the EUDR excludes land that is predominantly under 'agricultural use', it can be inferred that if a land is predominantly used under 'agroforestry systems' for the purposes spelled out by Recital (37), it cannot be considered as 'forest'. In this case and for the purpose of the Regulation, this land must be considered as being under 'agricultural use'. Regarding ancillary agricultural activities, including agroforestry activities in the context of restoration please see Section 2.

It would be relevant for the EU to here clarify that the existing JRC 'Forest' map does not (fully) recognize the consequences of this clause.

5. Clarification of land use in case of multiple land use types in the same area and the use of land registries and cadastral maps

In case a plot of land contains both **an area falling under the definition of 'forest' and an area which is 'agricultural use'**, the two areas are to be considered separately. The area fulfilling the criteria of the definition of 'forest' falls under the scope of the Regulation, while the area fulfilling the criteria of 'agricultural use', does not fall under the scope of the Regulation in terms of conversion.

Opinions and interpretations can differ on when such 'segregation' is applied – one would assume that the minimum area for 'forest' plays a role here. The "falling under the definition of 'forest'" is ambiguous.

² FAO World Programme For The Census Of Agriculture 2020, Vol. 1, p.120, point 8.12.12 and 8.12.13

...

In the assessment of whether a certain plot of land constitutes forest, the **actual forest properties** should prevail over the designation in land registers and cadastral maps.

How do “**actual forest properties**” differ from “**actual agroforestry properties**” ??

... The EU Observatory provided by the Commission is a free to use tool for all stakeholders to determine the global forest cover of 2020. However, the Observatory is non-exclusive, non-mandatory and carries no legal value. Public and private stakeholders can use any maps that they see fit for the purpose of their due diligence exercise or checks.

The JRC authors descriptions of the tool acknowledge the incomplete application of the EU forest definition, as what is mapped is primarily ‘tree cover’, while ‘agricultural use’ criterion is not visible.